

Photophysical behaviour of 1,1'-binaphthyl-2,2'-diol in different solvents and at various pH

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Analysis of absorption and fluorescence solvatochromic shifts of 1,1'-binaphthyl-2,2'-diol (2BNP) reveals that the molecule is twisted in S_0 state. A complete planarity of the molecule is not attained in S_1 state as in biphenyl or 1,1'-binaphthyl-4,4'-diol (4BNP). The attainment of planarity is also affected by hydrogen bonding interactions of the solvents. The monoanion is found to be non-fluorescent.

The geometry of the substituted molecules in the ground and excited states assume great significance in the understanding of photophysical and photochemical properties. The information about the ground state geometry can be obtained by diffraction, dipole moment and spectroscopic techniques¹. Experimentally the fluorimetric technique can provide information about the excited state geometry of the molecules. Werner's² extensive work is the important contribution toward the understanding of the relative geometries and solvent cages of ground and excited singlet states. Berlman³ reported that the absorption and fluorescence data can be used as a straight edge to provide quantitative evidence concerning the planarity of the molecules. By comparing the absorption and fluorescence spectra, Berlman proved that the biphenyl system was twisted in the ground state and attained planarity on excitation to S_1 state. The geometry change in biphenyl system on excitation had been used to explain the fluorescence characteristics of substituted biphenyls. A study of solvent and pH effects on absorption and fluorescence spectra of biphenyl carboxylic acids⁴, biphenylols⁵⁻⁸ and biphenylamines⁹⁻¹² revealed interesting features. The excited state behaviour of 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl¹⁰ was found to be similar to that of 2,7-diaminofluorene¹³ due to the change in geometry on excitation. In biphenyl-3-ol⁶ the interaction of -OH group at *m*-position with the phenyl ring was explained by geometry change. The dual emission of biphenyl-2-ol⁵ was reported to be due to interaction of -OH group with the π -cloud of the unsubstituted phenyl ring. This stimulated us to carry out a study on binaphthyl systems. In our earlier work we have investigated the luminescence characteristics of 1,1'-binaphthyl-4,4'-diol¹⁴. The present work reports the luminescence characteristics of 1,1'-binaphthyl-2,2'-diol in

different solvents and at various pH.

Results and discussion

Effect of solvents : The absorption and fluorescence data of 1,1'-binaphthyl-2,2'-diol (2BNP) in different solvents are compiled in Table 1 along with the spectral data of β -naphthol (β NP) and biphenyl-2,2'-diol (2DHBP). A comparative analysis of absorption solvatochromic shifts of 2BNP with 2DHBP⁷ and β -naphthol reveals that (i) the absorption spectrum of 2BNP is significantly red shifted to 2DHBP in all the solvents, (ii) a structured spectrum for 2BNP similar to β NP is obtained in cyclohexane, methanol and water, (iii) the red shifts of 2BNP relative to β NP in other solvents are minimum. The red shift observed in 2BNP relative to 2DHBP is due to the presence of addition of a phenyl ring. Generally a structured spectrum reveals the planarity of a molecule. The structured fluorescence spectrum of biphenyl was reported to be due to planar structure in the excited singlet state³ (S_1). The structured spectrum of 2BNP and close resemblance of its spectrum to β NP in other solvents indicate that the 2BNP molecule in the ground state is more twisted and exists as two β -naphthyl moieties. From the dipole moment study¹⁵ the dihedral angle in 2BNP is found to be 93°. To confirm this we have taken IR spectrum of 2BNP in potassium bromide pellet which gives a sharp peak at 3490 cm^{-1} and it is similar to the one obtained in 2,6-diphenylphenol¹⁶ and 2-hydroxybiphenyl¹⁷ where $\text{O}-\text{H}-\pi$ bonding was reported. This indicated that the presence of the $\text{O}-\text{H}-\pi$ intramolecular bonding in 2BNP as shown in Fig. 1. This type of bonding is possible only when the dihedral angle is around 90°.

In fluorescence, the maxima of 2BNP and 2DHBP are red shifted to β NP. As reported in biphenyl^{3,18} and 2DHBP⁷

Fig. 1

the 2BNP may attain planarity. This geometry change increases the delocalisation between the naphthyl moieties.

But we cannot expect the complete attainment of planarity as in biphenyl and 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl, since the OH group at *ortho* position will sterically affect the attainment of planarity. Furthermore in hydrogen bonding solvents the attainment of planarity (geometry change) is also affected due to the steric effect caused by solvent cage. Hence solvatochromic red shifts from cyclohexane to water for 2BNP and 2DHBP are less when compared to β NP (Table 1). The results show that in the excited state (S_1), the molecule is not as twisted as in ground state. The fluorescence maximum is significantly red shifted relative to β NP in all the solvents. The twisting is less or the molecule is more

Table 1. Absorption maxima (nm) and fluorescence maxima (nm) of 2BNP, 2DHBP and β NP in different solvents and at various acid concentrations

Solvent	2BNP		β NP		2DHBP	
	λ_{abs}	λ_{flu}	λ_{abs}	λ_{flu}	λ_{abs}	λ_{flu}
Cyclohexane	332.2	326(s)	330.0	336	279.2	343.5
	328.0	357.1	320.0			
	318.0		300.0			
	289.0		285.0			
	277.8		275.0			
	268.0		265.0			
	226.0		215.0			
Dioxane	334.8	329.5			243.0	350.0
	323.0	358.0			282.0	
	289.0					
	277.8					
	267.0					
	237.8					
Ethyl acetate	335.0	326.1			283.8	348.5
	321.0	358.0				
	289.0					
	277.2					
	267.0					
Chloroform	332.2	328.0			245.2	353.0
	319.0	362.9			280.6	
	290.5					
	278.2					
	270.0					
Dichloro-methane	332.4	327.1			244.0	349.5
	318.0	361.9			279.0	
	289.5					
	278.2					
	267.5					
	233.8					

<i>t</i> -Butanol	335.2	326.0			245.0	350.0
	324.0	361.4			285.0	
	289.0					
	277.0					
	268.0					
Acetonitrile	226.0					349.0
	335.0	327.0			243.0	
	321.5	360.1			279.0	
	289.5					
	277.2					
Isopropyl alcohol	267.5					352.5
	226.8					
	334.8	329.0			244.0	
	324.0	363.0			284.0	
	289.5					
Methanol	277.8					351.0
	267.0					
	227.0					
	335.8	326(s)	340.0	352.0	244.0	
	325.0	364.1	320.0		281.4	
	290.0		285.0			
Glycol	277.0		275.0			348.5
	269.0		265.0			
	230.0		210.0			
	335.0	326.0			242.2	
	325.5	362.0			283.4	
	290.0					
Water	278.2					358.0
	268.0					
	229.8					
	332.6	348(s)	326.4	350-360	278.2	
	320(s)	369.4	315(s)		307.2	
	289.5		283.0			
Monoanion	277.0		273.0			399.0
	268.0		264.0			
	225.8		225.6			
	358.0		343.0	420		
			291.0			
			280.8			
		272(s)				
		248.0				

planar in cyclohexane when compared with other hydrogen bonding solvents. This is also revealed by the large red shift of 2BNP in cyclohexane relative to other solvents. When we compare the fluorescence maximum of 2BNP and

β NP the shift in cyclohexane is 21.1 nm but in methanol and water the shifts are less (12.1 and 14.1 nm). The solvent interaction of OH group which restricts the attainment of planarity in 2BNP was also confirmed by the compari-

son of its solvatochromic shifts with 1,1'-binaphthyl-4,4'-diol (4BNP). The solvatochromic shift of 4BNP¹⁴ from cyclohexane (379.7) to methanol (404.8) is larger (25.1 nm) than 2BNP (7 nm). This is because the solvent interaction of OH group will not affect the attainment of planarity in 4BNP.

Analysis of solvatochromic shifts of 2BNP reveals that the shifts in absorption are less but fluorescence maxima are continuously red shifted with the increase in polarity and hydrogen bonding ability of the solvents. The Stokes' shifts of 2BNP in various solvents are given in Table 2. When we compare the Stokes' shifts with the solvent parameters $E_T(30)$ ¹⁹ and BK²⁰ values, the Stokes' shifts are more in accordance with $E_T(30)$ than BK values. This shows that hydrogen bonding interactions are predominant than solvent polarity effects. A good linear correlation with $E_T(30)$ is expected if the molecule has only intermolecular hydrogen bonding interaction and also if it does not undergo any geometry change. In diphenylamine we observed a good correlation with $E_T(30)$ and in *N*-methyl diphenylamine a good correlation was observed with BK values⁹. Both molecules do not undergo geometry change and in diphenylamine hydrogen bonding interactions are predominant whereas in *N*-methyl diphenylamine solvent polarity effects are predominant. In 2BNP the poor correlation for both parameters is due to the presence of both inter and intramolecular hydrogen bonding and geometry change during excitation.

Table 2. Stokes' shifts (cm^{-1}) observed for 2BNP in different solvents with $E_T(30)$ and BK values

Solvent	$\overline{\Delta\nu}_{ss}$	$E_T(30)$	BK
Cyclohexane	2099	31.6	-0.001
Dioxane	1936	36.0	0.043
Ethyl acetate	1918	38.1	-
Chloroform	2547	39.1	0.372
Dichloromethane	2452	41.1	0.586
<i>t</i> -Butanol	2163	43.9	0.673
Acetonitrile	2081	46.0	0.864
Isopropyl alcohol	2320	48.6	0.766
Methanol	2315	55.5	0.858
Glycol	2226	56.3	-
Water	2995	63.1	0.913
Correlation coefficient		0.6195	0.4846

Effect of proton concentration : The absorption and fluorescence spectra of 2BNP in the $H_0/pH/H_-$ range of -10 to 17 have been analysed. The absorption spectra of various prototropic species are shown in Fig. 2 and the absorption

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of 2BNP at different pH : (....) neutral species, (-.-.-) monoanion.

and fluorescence maxima of these species are listed in Table 1.

2BNP exists as a neutral species at pH 7 with the absorption maximum at 332.6 nm. With the decrease of pH from 7, the absorption spectra of 2BNP is not affected upto H_0-5 ($10 M H_2SO_4$). When the pH is increased to 11 the absorption maximum is red shifted to 358.0 nm (Fig. 2). A clear isosbestic point ($\lambda = 340$ nm) indicates the equilibrium between two species in the ground state. Hence the red shifted maximum is due to monoanion formed by the deprotonation of one of the hydroxy group. Further increase in basicity does not produce any change in the absorption maxima of 2BNP as there is no dianion formation.

The fluorescence spectrum of 2BNP is the same from the $H_0 = -5$ to pH 7. So the fluorescence spectrum with the maximum at 369.4 nm is due to the neutral species. When the pH is increased, the quenching of fluorescence starts around pH 8 and it is completed around pH 12. No fluorescence was observed with the increase of the basicity upto $H_- 17$. This shows that the monoanion is formed around pH 10 and it is non-fluorescent.

Acidity constants : The pK_a value for the neutral-monoanion equilibrium was calculated spectrophotometrically for 2BNP and is listed in Table 3. The pK_a^* value for this equilibrium in the S_1 state for 2BNP was determined with the help of Förster cycle method²¹ using only absorption maxima of neutral form (332.6 nm) and monoanion (358 nm) since the monoanion is non-fluorescent. Fluorescence titration was carried out by exciting the molecule at

Table 3. Ground and excited singlet state acidity constants of 2BNP

Equilibrium	pK _a	pK _a [*] (FT)	Förster cycle method		
			pK _a [*] (abs)	pK _a [*] (flu)	pK _a [*] (ave)
Neutral – Monoanion	10.2	9.8	5.72 ^a	–	–

^aNeutral – 332.6 nm, Monoanion – 358.0 nm.

isosbestic wavelength (340 nm) and measuring fluorescence intensities of the neutral form at 369 nm. The fluorescence titration curve was obtained for the neutral form (Fig. 3). The pK_a^{*} value was determined from the mid-point of the curve. The Förster cycle pK_a^{*}(abs) (Table 3) shows that the molecule becomes more acidic in the S₁ state. But pK_a^{*}(FT) is close to ground state pK_a value indicating that the life-time of the species is so small and the rate of deprotonation cannot compete with the rate of emission. This is the reason why the excited state equilibrium is not attained at pH 5.2 though the molecule becomes more acidic in S₁ state.

Fig. 3. Plot of relative fluorescence intensities (I/I_0) vs pH of 2BNP.

Experimental

1,1'-Binaphthyl-2,2'-diol (Aldrich) was purified by repeated crystallization from toluene. All solvents used were of spectrograde or AnalaR. Triple-distilled water was used for the preparation of aqueous solutions. Solutions in the pH range 1.5–12 were prepared by adding appropriate amount of NaOH and H₃PO₄. A modified Hammett's acidity scale (H_0)²² for solutions below pH 1 and Yagil's basicity scale (H_-)²³ for solutions above pH 12 were employed. The solutions were prepared just before taking measure-

ments. The concentrations of the solutions were of the order 10⁻⁴–10⁻⁵ M. The absorption spectra were recorded using a Jasco UNIDEC-7800 spectrophotometer and fluorescence measurements were made using a Jasco FP-550 spectrofluorimeter. An Elico LI-IOT pH meter was used.

Conclusions :

1,1'-Binaphthyl-2,2'-diol is found to be twisted and it exists as two β-naphthyl moieties in the ground state (S₀). The O–H–π intramolecular bonding is observed in the S₀ state. The twisting is reduced on excitation and the molecule is more planar in cyclohexane than in other solvents in S₁ state. The monoanion is found to be non-fluorescent. The molecule becomes more acidic in the S₁ state.

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Kothai Nayaki *et al.* : Photophysical behaviour of 1,1'-binaphthyl-2,2'-diol in different solvents *etc.*

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